

ANALYSIS OF BODY SIZE DIFFERENCES OF LOCAL HORSES IN XINJIANG AND EVALUATION OF MEAT INDEX

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13860198>

Abstract. *This study aims to clarify the body shape, appearance, and meat consumption of the four existing local horse breeds in Xinjiang, as well as the newly discovered horses in two regions. The analysis was conducted using linear body shape analysis, discriminant analysis, and other methods. The results indicate that Barkol horses are small in size (with a body height of 130.50 cm), making them suitable for tourism riding or mountain endurance riding. Kazakh horses in the Ili area are appropriate for riding, while Kazakh horses in the Altay area are better suited for endurance riding and product production (with an average HMPI of 2.65; they have a well-developed chest, although the rump requires strengthening). Taxkorgan local horses are also suitable for riding. Kirgiz horses excel in speed riding or endurance riding. Mountain-type Yanqi horses are ideal for mountain riding or product production, whereas plain-type Yanqi horses are suitable for riding. Additionally, Hotan local horses are appropriate for endurance riding or tourist riding. The interspecific differences in body shape characteristics among Xinjiang local horse breeds are pronounced. Discriminant analysis effectively distinguishes various local horse breeds based on their physical appearance.*

Keywords: *local varieties; uses; production performance; body size index.*

1 Introduction

Horses, as the first of the six domesticated animals, were once widely utilized in various aspects of life. However, with the advancement of mechanization and informatization, the role of horses in agriculture and animal husbandry has diminished, leading to their gradual transformation into a component of the modern horse industry. Kazakh horses are primarily found in the Ili, Tacheng, Altay, and Wuchang regions of northern Xinjiang, China. The Kirgiz horse is a plateau breed cultivated by the Kirgiz ethnic group, predominantly produced in the alpine grasslands of the Kizilsu Kirgiz Autonomous Prefecture in Xinjiang. The Barkol horse is mainly located in Barkol Kazakh Autonomous County and is a grassland herding breed that has evolved through long-term domestication and crossbreeding with local breeds such as Kazakh and Mongolian horses, particularly during periods of ethnic migration and military service. This breed exhibits unique herding characteristics. The Yanqi horse can be categorized into mountain and plain types based on its origin and distribution. The mountain type is found in the Bayinbuluke grassland, Hejing County, and Tianshan pasture in Heshuo County, adapted to the grassland ecology at altitudes of 2500 meters. In contrast, the plain type Yanqi horse refers to a hybrid breed of several horse breeds distributed across Yanqi County, Bohu County, Korla City, Yuli County, and Heshuo County. The Hotan local horse, with its distinct appearance, is found in the Hotan area and differs

significantly from the four local breeds in Xinjiang. The 'Tashkorgan local horse' is a breed located in Taxkorgan Tajik Autonomous County, notable for its curled ears and potential relation to the Indian Marwari horse.

Phenotype is a crucial trait in animals, as it reflects significant information regarding the animal's ancestry, evolutionary history, habitat, and nutritional conditions. The diverse resources and dynamic environment of Xinjiang have fostered the emergence of unique species, including horses. Currently, most research on horse functional traits concentrates on sport horses that offer greater economic benefits, while there is comparatively less focus on the production traits of horses related to agricultural output. This study examines the production performance of local horse breeds by measuring their body dimensions, and it provides recommendations for future breeding planning.

2 Methods

This experiment selected eight sampling locations, all of which were pastoral areas with grazing as the feeding condition. A total of 1,380 adult horses, all in good health and well-developed, were measured and evaluated. The table below details the sampling locations. Various methods were employed to measure the body size index of each horse, including a soft ruler (accuracy: 0.1 cm), a horse measuring stick (accuracy: 0.1 cm), a holding frame, horse rope, horse head harness, water rein, and a body measurement statistical table. Twelve body measurements were taken: body height, body length, chest circumference, tube circumference, head length, forehead width, neck length, chest depth, chest width, hip height, hip width, and jaw concavity. Measurements were conducted under conditions where the field was flat and the horse was in a correct stance. The Horse Meat Purpose Index (HMPI) is based on and refined from the meat index calculation method proposed by Zhang Yinghan for classifying cattle breed types. The meat index of a horse is defined as the ratio of the average live weight (kg) to the average body height (cm) of a breed or group after reaching three years of age. A discriminant analysis was conducted on Xinjiang local breed horses. After preliminary statistical analysis of the data obtained from the tests using Excel 2010, SPSS 20.0 was employed to perform one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), discriminant analysis, and calculation of the coefficient of variation. The meat consumption index of all horses was calculated using a specific formula, with results expressed as "mean \pm standard deviation" and significant differences indicated by letter marking.

3 Results and discussion

(1)The results of the analysis of body size differences among six local breeds of horse mares from Xinjiang are presented in Table 2-1. The table indicates that the body sizes are arranged from largest to smallest as follows: Mountain-type Yanqi horse > Plain-type Yanqi horse > Kirgiz horse > Kazakh horses from the Altay region > Kazakh horses from the Ili region > Taxkorgan local horses > Barkol horses > Hotan local horses. The Kazakh horses from the Altay region are characterized by a long body, thick build, deep chest, and well-developed rump, exhibiting traits typical of draft horses. In contrast, Kazakh horses from the Ili area possess thin builds, deep chests, and wide hindquarters, representing a dual-purpose type that is closer to riding horses. Barkol horses are noted for their well-developed chests, thick builds, and long bodies, also classifying them as draft horses. The Mountain-type Yanqi horse features a well-developed chest, thick build, and large head, serving as a dual-purpose horse similar to draft horses. The Plain-type Yanqi horse is characterized by a well-developed chest, long neck, and thin build, functioning as a dual-purpose horse with more pronounced mountainous haunches. The Yanqi horse exhibits a well-developed chest, while the Kirgiz horse is distinguished by its well-developed chest, long body, thin build,

and well-developed rump, making it a dual-purpose horse akin to riding horses, although it has a slightly shorter neck. The Hotan local horse has a well-developed chest and thick build, while the Taxkorgan local horses are characterized by small heads and wide mounds, qualifying them as dual-purpose horses. The Taxkorgan local horse features a thick build, long body, small head, and long neck, also classifying it as a dual-purpose horse, closer to the riding type.

Table 2-1 Comparison of body size of mares of local breeds in Xinjiang

Items	KA	KY	YQS	YQP	KE	BLK	KL	TX
height	134.6	132.7	138.82	136.50	135.4	130.50	128.42	131.29
	4	3	±2.29 ^a	±1.67 ^b	0	±1.66 ^d	±3.86 ^d	±1.38 ^d
body length	148.7	138.0	147.30	143.56	148.1	139.57	139.79	142.29
	4	0	±3.95 ^a	±2.23 ^b	0	±3.55 ^c	±7.44 ^c	±3.95 ^c
chest	165.8	160.7	186.07	163.41	161.6	158.57	154.29	152.57
	0	3	±7.14 ^a	±4.53 ^{bc}	1	±6.70 ^{cd}	±5.52 ^{de}	±7.39 ^e
perimeter	18.01	17.02	18.75	17.28	17.64	17.57	17.26	16.57
	±0.89 ^b	±0.48 ^d	±0.65 ^a	±0.68 ^{cd}	±0.86 ^b	±0.53 ^{bc}	±0.94 ^{cd}	±1.13 ^c
neck length	57.75	56.93	63.75	63.38	57.93	55.43	56.38	60.93
	±3.33 ^c	±4.26 ^c	±3.23 ^a	±2.01 ^a	±3.37 ^c	±4.28 ^c	±3.37 ^c	±3.83 ^b
head length	54.55	50.38	56.02	54.66	52.04	50.86	50.29	50.50
	±2.03 ^a	±7.01 ^b	±2.35 ^a	±1.10 ^a	±2.23 ^b	±2.54 ^b	±1.51 ^b	±2.17 ^b
width of forehead	18.94	18.75	18.69	19.20	19.28	19.71	19.00	19.17
	±0.80 ^a	±0.79 ^b	±0.48 ^b	±0.56 ^{ab}	±1.00 ^a	±1.11 ^a	±1.02 ^{ab}	±0.98 ^{ab}
maxillofacial	8.61	7.45	7.69	7.93	8.11	7.43	7.79	7.83
recess	±1.23 ^a	±1.24 ^b	±0.70 ^{ab}	±0.70 ^{ab}	±1.28 ^a	±1.62 ^b	±1.37 ^{ab}	±1.17 ^{ab}
chest width	36.73	36.00	41.57	37.66	34.67	37.86	35.04	34.83
	±1.29 ^b	±7.43 ^b	±2.59 ^a	±1.93 ^b	±	±3.29 ^b	±2.73 ^{cd}	±1.47 ^d
chest depth	65.62	69.25	64.75	66.22	62.29	68.86	63.00±	61.33
	±4.16 ^b	±4.31 ^a	±2.93 ^{bc}	±4.74 ^{ab}	±2.66 ^d	±2.04 ^a	2.22 ^{cd}	±5.29 ^d
coccyx	132.4	131.9	137.02	134.34	133.2	128.50	126.17	127.33
	6	8	±2.81 ^a	±1.62 ^b	1	±1.66 ^d	±3.61 ^e	±2.25 ^{de}
tailbone width	46.73	47.32	52.25	50.06	50.47	45.50	47.29	47.00
	±2.55 ^c	±3.74 ^c	±2.27 ^a	±2.99 ^b	±0.94 ^a	±2.90 ^c	±1.96 ^c	±1.55 ^c

Note: No letters in the same row or the same letter in the data shoulder label indicate that the difference is not significant ($P > 0.05$). In contrast, different lowercase letters signify significant differences ($P < 0.05$). The abbreviations used are as follows: KA refers to the Kazakh horse from the Altay region, KY denotes the Kazakh horse from the Ili region, YQS indicates the mountain type Yanqi horse, YQP represents the plain type Yanqi horse, KE stands for the Kirgiz horse, BLK is the Barkol horse, KL refers to the Hotan Local horse, and TX represents the Taxkorgan local horse. This notation is consistent with the table below.

(2)The comparison of body size indices among local horse breeds in Xinjiang is presented in Table 2-2. Arranged from largest to smallest, the breeds are as follows: Plain type Yanqi horse, Mountain type Yanqi horse, Kirgiz horse, Altay region Kazakh horse, Ili region Kazakh horse, Tashkorgan region horse, Barkol horse, and Hotan local horse. Notably, there is a significant difference in body length between the two types of Kazakh horses, which is distinct from all other horse breeds. The body length index of Kazakh horses from Ili is the smallest, showing a significant difference when compared to the Barkol horse. The chest circumference of the Mountain type Yanqi horse measures 189.94 cm, which is significantly different from that of all other horse breeds. Similarly, the chest circumference of the Plain type Yanqi horse is 175.56 cm,

also significantly different from other breeds. Both Tashkorgan local horses and Hotan local horses exhibit the smallest chest circumferences, with no significant difference observed between them. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in the chest circumferences of Kazakh horses from the two regions.

Table 2-2 Comparison of body size of stallions of local breeds in Xinjiang

Items (cm)	KA	KY	YQS	YQP	KE	BLK	KL	TX
height	139.4	139.12	144.06	144.63	140.22	134.14	131.55	136.30
	1	±1.55 ^b	±3.52 ^a	±2.02 ^a	±2.34 ^b	±1.80 ^c	±3.98 ^d	±1.25 ^c
body length	151.9	143.90	151.09	150.56	148.87	143.21	140.18	142.90
	3	±2.62 ^b	±4.80 ^a	±3.21 ^a	±3.98 ^a	±4.02 ^{bc}	±3.19 ^c	±3.70 ^{bc}
chest	168.2	167.88	189.94	175.56	161.47	162.14	154.36	155.30
	6	±3.39 ^c	±8.11 ^a	±6.12 ^b	±6.15 ^d	±4.45 ^d	±5.32 ^e	±4.03 ^e
perimeter	18.55	18.37	20.00	19.63	18.49	18.31	18.36	17.90
	±0.88 ^b	±0.37 ^{bc}	±0.77 ^a	±0.84 ^a	±0.99 ^{bc}	±0.71 ^{bc}	±0.71 ^b	±0.94 ^c
neck length	59.27	60.22	65.20	65.96	56.42	55.41	56.41	60.10
	±4.06 ^b	±0.97 ^b	±2.60 ^a	±1.60 ^a	±1.50 ^c	±4.00 ^c	±2.06 ^c	±2.81 ^b
head length	56.60	54.67	57.43	57.26	47.50	52.43	50.77	52.70
	±2.10 ^a	±1.58 ^b	±2.21 ^a	±1.38 ^a	±1.64 ^e	±1.99 ^{cd}	±1.92 ^d	±2.21 ^c
width of forehead	18.93	18.78	19.33	18.81	18.00	19.43	19.00	19.70
	±0.80 ^b	±0.67 ^b	±0.49 ^{ab}	±0.54 ^b	±0.63 ^c	±1.27 ^{ab}	±0.63 ^a	±0.82 ^a
maxillofacial recess	8.73	7.33	8.47	8.13	8.67	8.29	8.14	7.80
	±0.80 ^a	±0.50 ^c	±0.64 ^{ab}	±0.62 ^{ab}	±0.82 ^a	±1.25 ^{ab}	±0.90 ^a	±0.63 ^{bc}
chest width	39.43	35.89	43.51	42.15	38.17	35.29	35.91	38.70
	±2.34 ^b	±1.05 ^c	±2.43 ^a	±2.66 ^a	±1.72 ^c	±1.87 ^c	±3.24 ^c	±2.54 ^b
chest depth	67.60	69.00	66.06	71.41	65.33	67.80	62.73	65.10
	±3.02 ^a	±0.87 ^{ab}	±2.68 ^{bc}	±10.04	±1.21 ^{bc}	±2.18 ^{ab}	±4.36 ^c	±0.74 ^{bc}
coccyx	135.4	137.03	140.66	144.11	137.00	132.43	128.92	134.40
	7	±2.05 ^c	±4.28 ^b	±3.51 ^a	±1.55 ^c	±1.59 ^d	±3.70 ^e	±1.17 ^{cd}
tailbone width	47.80	50.33	53.20	52.74	47.67	48.86	46.41	46.30
	±3.17 ^c	±3.40 ^b	±2.31 ^a	±2.14 ^a	±1.51 ^{cd}	±3.48 ^{bc}	±1.59 ^d	±1.25 ^d

(3)Discriminant analysis effectively classifies local horse breeds based on body measurement data. Fisher's discriminant method is employed to categorize Xinjiang local breeds using parameters such as body height, body length, chest circumference, tube circumference, neck length, chest width, chest depth, rump width, and rump height. Mares were included in the discriminant analysis. The results indicate that the centroid points of horse breeds from different regions are distinctly separated. Notably, the Kirgiz horse and the mountain-type Yanqi horse are positioned far apart, exhibiting significant differences in their body shape characteristics compared to the other four regions. The analysis clearly differentiates horse breeds from various regions, with some breeds closely clustered together, demonstrating ideal results. Furthermore, discriminant analysis was performed on Xinjiang local breed stallions, revealing that the centroid points of horse breeds from different regions remain clearly distinguished, with notable variations in body shape characteristics among the breeds. The Kirgiz horse stands out, being distanced from all other breeds, while the two types of Yanqi horses exhibit differences in their body shape characteristics. Additionally, the Kazakh horses from the two regions display considerable variation in body shape, which effectively highlights the interspecific distance among local horse breeds.

(4)Table 2-6 presents the HMPI (meat consumption index) for local breed horses in Xinjiang. The HMPI values for male horses range from 2.33 to 3.52, with the mountain type Yanqi horses exhibiting the highest HMPI. For female horses, the HMPI is ranked from highest to lowest as follows: mountain type Yanqi horses, Altay area Kazakh horses, plain type Yanqi horses, Ili area Kazakh horses, Kirgiz horses, Barkol horses, Hotan local horses, and Taxkorgan local horses. Notably, the HMPI of mountain type Yanqi horses is significantly greater than that of other horse breeds, indicating superior meat quality. Conversely, the Taxkorgan local horse and Hotan local horse have the lowest HMPI values, suggesting that these two breeds demonstrate poor meat performance.

Table 2-6 weight, body height and HMPI of Xinjiang local horse

5 Conclusion

Items	male			female			HMPI
	Average weight	Average height	HMP I	Average weight	Average height		
HSA	370.44	139.41	2.66	354.94	134.64	4	2.6
HSY	368.04	139.12	2.65	323.00	132.73	3	2.4
YQS	507.02	144.06	3.52	482.64	138.82	8	3.4
YQP	416.43	144.63	2.88	339.88	136.50	9	2.4
KK	327.66	140.22	2.34	328.54	135.40	3	2.4
BK	331.88	134.14	2.47	309.39	130.50	7	2.3
HT	282.87	131.55	2.15	282.43	128.42	0	2.2
TS	288.79	136.30	2.12	271.59	131.29	7	2.0

The distance between species of local horses in various places has been better verified from the physical characteristics. The results show that the two types of Yanqi horses are far apart, which is consistent with their historical origins. There are great differences in the physical characteristics of Yanqi horses in mountainous and plain living environments. The Barkol horse was bred as a draft horse and is closer to the Mongolian horse. It can explain the reason for the long distance from other horse breeds; the Kirgiz horse’s living environment is closed, and its body shape characteristics are very different from other horse breeds; the body shape of Kazakh horses in the two regions is also different. This study’s evaluation of the meat consumption index of local horse breeds shows that the Yanqi horse The meat performance of Kazakh horse is better. Xinjiang local horse breeds have diverse phenotypes, and targeted breeding can be carried out based on different appearance characteristics. Yanqi horses and Kazakh horses are suitable for product production. Kazakh horses in the Altay region can be bred for coat color; Kirgiz horses, Hotan local horses and Taxkorgan local horses Suitable for riding direction, especially endurance riding or touring riding; Barkol horse is suitable for meat or touring riding direction. The

interspecific discriminant analysis of local horse breeds in Xinjiang is clear, and there are obvious differences in body shape and appearance among various breeds.

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